

IMPORTANCE AND CLASSIFICATION OF INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation

The purpose of the research is to highlight the cases in which the use of interactive methods should be emphasized and to identify the types of interactive methods that can be effectively used in the organization of lessons on a planned basis. One of the tasks of the research was to study the use of interactive methods, to identify the differences and similarities of these methods and to illustrate their important factors with examples.

Keywords

Interactive teaching methods, heuristic conversation, debate, mental attack.

Introduction

In the developed period, the interactive methods proposed by the teaching methodology in the process of organizing the lesson using non-traditional methods are based on their high effectiveness in the educational process. Accordingly, the basic concepts of teaching in teaching methods are developed and the use of interactive methods is carried out through these issues. There are many of them, the most important of which are¹:

¹ Akbarova Sh. A. “Interactive Method of Teaching” article, 2018//

<http://manzura90.zn.uz/interfaol-metodlar/>

a) Interactive methods are action-based and encourage students to act and be active, in which process the teacher must be the right organizer.

b) interactive methods are based on results, in which students participate as subjects of learning activities, the purpose of the lesson should be achieved;

c) a key indicator of successful learning, the result of which is aimed at developing students' thinking skills and the ability to creatively solve practical problems, to find a free and independent way in scientific and practical problems, thereby together interactive methods should be material based on thinking;

d) the educational issue should be a unit of educational activity. Of all the other issues that arise in life, it is a learning tactic that differs in that it focuses primarily on mastering the ways of thinking and acting, rather than on changing its subject, but on changing the subject itself²;

e) the process of educational activity is the student's efforts to solve educational problems in the form of the transfer of their actions in the content of the external subject to the internal mental appearance (internalization), the type of personal knowledge, skills and the formation of skills;

f) the acquisition of cognitive skills and abilities - these are mental actions, which are performed by the individual in the form of a form based on external means, and as a result of learning activities, reorganized subject-based subject consists of actions.

Teaching based on attitudes and movements of learning activities is called this interactive teaching method³. An important role is played by the student and the

² Abdukodirov AA, Ishmukhamedov R., Pardaev A. Innovative technologies in education (practical recommendations for teachers of educational institutions) .- T .: Iste'dod, 2008.-180 pages.

³ Badmayev M. Methods of teaching psychology. M. "Vlados" 2001

teacher, who do not read as a separate subject, but work together with the group, discuss and discuss issues with each other.

Methods

In the research process, we used analysis, synthesis methods (in order to highlight the importance of using interactive methods in the organization of lessons and to identify the most effective and therefore widely used types of newly introduced interactive methods). We also use the classification method (to explain the importance and types of interactive methods introduced and recommended by scientists in the examples and the lessons and tasks that need to be considered in the lesson), the system method (research materials to for plash)⁴. Induction and deduction methods have also been used in part.

Results

The interactive method is a joint creative and productive activity of teachers and students, not only the process of individual collaboration, but also the emergence of the process of cognitive research. The teacher should always keep in mind that it is important to always include the "teacher-student" system, not only in the direction of active learning, but also in the direction of active learning, without asking questions on their own. .

The following interactive methods are active methods with their effectiveness and fun: heuristic conversation; method of debate; mental attack; round table.

Method of heuristic conversation

One of the methods of interactive teaching is **heuristic conversation**, which in Latin means “collect, seek”⁵. This method of conversation is based on an ancient Greek view of a teaching system called the Socrates conversation. In this way, skilful

⁴ Khaydarov F., N. Khalilova "Methods of teaching psychology". Aloqachi 2007

⁵ Akbarova Sh. A. “Interactive Method of Teaching” article, 2018//

questioning is directed and the reader is directed to find the correct answer to the question asked independently. The difference between this method of teaching and Socrates' is that it is widely used. But there are also aspects of its absolute similarity, the function of which, according to its description, is chosen to direct the reader to skilfully ask questions by actively thinking about them. By its very nature, heuristic dialogue is a collective thinking or conversation, a conversation as a seeker of a solution to a problem. In methodology, therefore, this method is considered to be one of the problem-based teaching methods, and the heuristic conversation is no different from the previous one from the so-called problem-seeking conversation. The methodology draws an individual quantitative boundary between them. If a heuristic conversation only applies to one element of a particular topic, the problems may be different. However, there are differences in this situation, if in practice the conversation is made real, it is impossible to notice this invisible difference between "only one" and "many" problems in the classroom: the conversation between teacher and audience turns into a multi-question conversation and the relevant conversation goes unnoticed. But now this is another method of teaching, which will be explained in the description of the next method. The point is that a thought-provoking search in a conversation becomes a team search, and in the search for a solution to a problem, the exchange of ideas, different options, conclusions between them, cooperation and consensus activate each other. Logically, this method is considered as an interactive teaching method.

The questions asked to turn a conversation into a heuristic conversation are also subject to conditions that other problem-based teaching methods follow. In the process of becoming a heuristic conversation, however, it is necessary to implement one of the interactive teaching methods⁶ that caused the problem situation.

Method of debate

⁶ "National Program of Personnel Training" T., 1997

Nowadays, the “**debate**” interactive teaching method is widely used to organize the teaching content, and the quality is noticeable.

The discussion method looks like a heuristic conversation, or rather a specially programmed free theoretical question is discussed, usually starting as a heuristic conversation by asking a question. It is a norm in the classroom that it is always debated. Debate is a dialogic form of activity, the creation of a fierce struggle⁷, a conversation, between different opinions. The exchange of ideas does not go as consistently and weightily as in a normal conversation, while in a debate the collision of one idea with another has a somewhat nervous appearance. A distinctive feature of the debate is that the idea of the debate is that those who argue actively think or prove the point with evidence. Debate and reasoning are understood to be causal connections in activities, an approach proposed by L.S. Vygotsky, but those who examined speech activity did not dwell on it, especially those who did not analyze the interdependence of thinking and dialogue in problematic debate.

Usually, thinking gives rise to an answer to the argument of the complainant in the debate, so it is assumed that different opinions give rise to the argument. As a result, the situation is quite the opposite: the debate activates the notion that the debate generates the idea, and the discussion debates provide a mastery of the masterpiece as a product of thinking. The interdependence of such debate and thinking is shown in the research of the famous psychologist AK Markov.

Method of mental attack

The method of "**mental attack**" has not yet been widely used as a teaching method in the practice of higher education, this method is the result of the management system⁸, as well as scientific research. It is widely used in economic management activities, in particular. The importance of this method is that, in the

⁷Akbarova Sh. A. “Interactive Method of Teaching” article, 2018//

⁸Khaydarov F., N. Khalilova "Methods of teaching psychology". Aloqachi 2007

opinion of experts, the ideas that come directly to the brain in search of an answer to the problem, assumptions include random comparisons, as well as sudden, existing, necessary and unnecessary connections. A random sentence recorded on a dictaphone is then used to carefully analyze the ideas, especially those that are close to the interesting method of mental attack, and then to ask and discuss a deeper question. There is a golden rule of mental attack - do not doubt any of what the participants say during the conversation, but give them complete freedom of expression. Such freedom allows one to behave calmly, not to be ashamed of “group opinion,” not to be afraid to put oneself in an awkward position. In this case, unexpected, but necessary, really intense thoughts arise. That is why a mental attack is organized. How can this method be used in higher education? It should be noted that the range of possibilities is not sufficient to apply in all types of teaching. But the mental attack method can be used to explain the difficulties of solving a problem. For example: some economic problems (wage arrears, voluntary tax payments of enterprises, etc.), in sociology (interpretation of the rating of political activity) in pedagogy (the conflict between morality and immorality), in psychology, the laws of mental development and education⁹. educational practices, military situations in the military field and measures to protect society from danger, etc.

Method of round table

The round table method entered pedagogy from political science. The roundtable will be organized by representatives of political and scientific circles. The exchange of ideas allows us to find some points of clarity, as it serves to guide the general conclusion in their subsequent work - to achieve scientific truth or political stability. The round table method is used to increase the effectiveness of problem solving with the help of different scientific aspects, different professions of

⁹ Turdiev N.SH., Asadov YU.M., Akbarova S.N., Temirov D.SH. Educational technologies aimed at developing students' competencies in the general secondary education system. // Textbook. (Part I). Tashkent, 2015. - 160 b; B. 5-6 b.

theoretical problems of teaching. For example, in a special section for law students, a science teacher for students studying the personality and activities of a lawyer examined a seminar on "criminal behavior" by the method of a round table¹⁰. During the training, he asks the same questions as the lawyer on criminal conduct, clarifies opinions, explains, gives examples. The science teacher, on the other hand, is “a beginner at the round table, a lawyer - making a series of additions to ideas. This is necessary because legal questions, especially the specific rights of people (victim or criminal, judge, witness, etc.) and the moral assessment of people's criminal behavior based on the subject and purpose of science, are the subject of the whole course. but also the aspect of the science being studied. The discussion of such questions is active not only because of the participation of a legal scholar, but also because their legal knowledge of crime and the richness of the vocabulary can be used as material for analysis. In this way, the topic is considered from two perspectives - from the point of view of law and the science being studied, so the topic is studied in depth. It found its proof in the exam. Among other topics, students cite examples from a given topic. In particular, the issues of criminal conduct discussed at the round table will be explained in detail, regardless of what questions are asked on the ticket during the exam. The lawyer's personality and activities showed that he was well mastered. The round table method is also used in another form. For example, it can hold a roundtable discussion with a study group. It is important to choose a topic that requires in-depth in-depth analysis in general and is considered comprehensively in terms of interests within the specialty. A similar training was conducted in higher education institutions with a group of invited teachers and students in their field. For example, the roundtable will be held in cooperation with international universities.

¹⁰ Abdukodirov AA, Ishmukhamedov R., Pardaev A. Innovative technologies in education (practical recommendations for teachers of educational institutions) .- T .: Iste'dod, 2008.-180 pages.

A variety of forms can be implemented in targeted training of the round table method. If an important condition in this regard is strict observance, it is necessary to keep in mind that the perceived need to consider multifaceted theoretical problems from the centre of attention to practical life. If there is no such need or there is, but it is understood in all respects, then the round table will become a normal, a seminar where everyone speaks their own language and there can be no competition.

Method of business game

The **business game** method first emerged in management practices, not in training systems¹¹. Currently, the business game method is used in various fields, in creative activities, in project design, in team work in real situations, as well as in military work. The “business game” method is a military game as a method of training, practitioners have long used military action in the form of a game to train the army, not in real combat battles, but in imitation of combat conditions.

In higher education, business games are used to train professionals of different professions in more management activities. This method is sometimes referred to as “business games” in management. In general, the essence of the method of business play - writes, one of the experts in this field EA Khursky - we can say that the method of intonation (imitation, reflection) is the management of various situations through play¹². Although such clarity is given in the instructional manual for the teacher, it is a question of whether the business game method is a method of learning to manage students rather than a real management method. In our view, the business game method can be applied not only in management, but also in the management of inference. In general, given the positive nature of this method, it can be used in any

¹¹ Turdiev N.SH., Asadov YU.M., Akbarova S.N., Temirov D.SH. Educational technologies aimed at developing students' competencies in the general secondary education system. // Textbook. (Part I). Tashkent, 2015. - 160 b; B. 5-6 b.

¹² Khaydarov F., N. Khalilova "Methods of teaching psychology". Aloqachi 2007

teaching as a teaching of all activities. The essence of the business game method is to study students as a model of teaching activities, as future professionals are trained to respond to their professional tasks. If we talk about the training of personnel in military universities, then the teaching of special subjects can play a key role in any situation. In this case, students can act in different roles: teacher, methodologist, inspector of the Department of Education, specialist in the field, practical student and even the student can be pre-planned and practical training in such a method of business games.

The teacher’s focus is on internal control to ensure that the activity is done correctly¹³. It was concluded that it is guided when the teacher directs it to the task. This means that in order to develop knowledge and skills through attention and nurturing, special attention should be paid to directing students to do the right activities as much as possible. This applies not only to the teaching of lessons, but also to the study of any mental and practical activity. The business game method is also more effective than other methods. Because it puts students in real situations and forces them to think clearly by skillfully playing the roles of specific individuals, and this situation directs students to increase their cognitive capacity, enabling them to better master topics and field terms.

Discussion

An important point to consider when organizing the learning process using interactive methods is the need to pay attention to the content of the task. Attention should be paid to the fact that the content of the task is different from the traditional forms of teaching. For example, assigning a group the task of obtaining a syllabus for a particular paragraph in a textbook is the exact opposite of the current educational requirement, as each student is able to do it on his or her own,

¹³ Richards, J., Rodgers, Theodore. *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching* (3rd Edition). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. pp. 23–24, 84–85. ISBN 978-1-107-67596-4. – 2014. Pp. 23-24.

independently. Research shows that simply setting a problem in a non-standard way encourages students to get help from each other, to know the opinions of others, and, as a result, to form a common opinion of the group. For example, students could be divided into small groups and asked to solve a small problem and create a system of answers.

At the end of the lesson it is necessary to organize the solution of the given problem on the basis of solutions of small problems of groups. As a result, it is possible to solve a complex problem in one lesson and involve more students in it.

Conclusion

When teaching the subjects in the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account the topics on which it is advisable to organize interactive lessons. This involves the use of one of the types of interactive sessions that will help you achieve the objectives of each session. For an interactive lesson to be effective, it is important to ensure that students know the basic concepts and background information on the topic before starting a new lesson. It is important to keep in mind that interactive learning takes more time for students to work independently than traditional learning.

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